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Effectiveness of repeated injections of botulinum toxin A on gait and fatigue in adults with spastic paraparesis secondary to multiple sclerosis

Aranzazu Vázquez-Doce, MD, PhD (ORCID: 0000-0003-0876-0867)

Department of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation, Hospital Universitario de La Princesa, Madrid, Spain

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Abstract

BACKGROUND: Multiple sclerosis (MS) is the most common neurologic disease in young adults. Spasticity is one of its most disabling symptoms, with botulinum toxin being one of the treatments of choice for this symptom.

OBJECTIVE: We assessed the response of botulinum toxin in improving walking ability and fatigue in patients with spastic paraparesis caused by MS.

METHODS: We performed a real-world, multicenter, prospective, open-label low-intervention trial in 84 patients with MS and spastic paraparesis of the lower limbs infiltrated with abobotulinumtoxinA (aboBoNT-A, Dysport®, Ipsen Pharma, France),

LINITOX. The response of spasticity, walking ability and fatigue is analyzed in 4 cycles of ultrasound-guided infiltration in the lower limbs.

RESULTS: The patients improved their walking ability by an average of 11.34% meters measured with 6-Minute Walk Test (6MWT), and decreased the percentage

of fatigue by 6.86% (4.66 percentage points less), in the 12-Item Multiple Sclerosis

Walking Scale (MSWS-12) 4 weeks after botulinum toxin infiltration, both values are statistically significant. This improvement seems to persist over time, throughout the cycles.

CONCLUSIONS: We found improved walking ability and less fatigue in patients with MS-related spastic paresis of the lower limbs after infiltration of aboBoNT-A.

Keywords: Multiple sclerosis, spasticity, fatigue, botulinum toxin, gait, quality of life

Introduction

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is the most common neurologic disease in young adults

(Walton et al, 2020). The most frequent symptoms of the disease are visual abnormalities, muscle weakness, sensory disorders, vertigo, incontinence, and cognitive impairment. These frequent and disabling symptoms also include fatigue (affecting more than 50% of patients), gait abnormalities, and spasticity or spastic syndrome (affecting up to 86% of patients). The association between fatigue and spasticity symptoms in the same patient is quite frequent. Spasticity is a sensorimotor disorder or motor phenomenon that presents as persistent involuntary muscle contraction (Feldman et al, 1980) and

muscle hyperactivity including dystonia, stiffness, and spasms (Dressler & Bigalke, 2017). Gait abnormalities in MS are multifactorial in origin, with fatigue being one of the most important factors and one of the most disabling symptoms. A marked association has been reported between spasticity and fatigue (Cameron et al, 2018).

Between 40% and 80% of patients with MS are affected by spasticity (Kuo and Hu, 2018; Thrower et al 2024), which considerably impairs quality of life. Spasticity of the lower limbs is one of the most common complaints in the early stages of MS (Flachenecker et al., 2014), with hypertonia of the triceps surae and adductors

leading to difficulty during the single support phase and high energy use while walking. The problem is compounded by poor flexion of the hip due to psoas major muscle involvement. Treatment of spasticity should be multifactorial, involving physiotherapy, occupational therapy, orthotic devices and technical aids, pharmacological treatment, or surgery. BoNT-A has proven effective for the treatment of spasticity of various causes and its associated symptoms (Miguens et al, 2023). It improves motor function, relieves pain, and facilitates rehabilitation. In adults, abobotulinumtoxinA (aboBoNT-A, Dysport®, Ipsen Pharma, France) is indicated for treatment of spasticity of the upper limbs and lower limbs in patients who have experienced a cerebrovascular accident (stroke), spasmodic torticollis, hemifacial spasm, and blepharospasm. While the literature reports abundant clinical evidence for the use of botulinum toxin, there are no specific data on its use for treatment of spasticity associated with MS or its impact on the ability to walk (Miguens et al, 2023).

Over the last 20 years, aboBoNT-A has been used at Hospital Universitario de La Princesa, Madrid, Spain, for compassionate treatment of spasticity of various causes, including spasticity of lower limbs in patients with MS, with considerable evidence of its clinical efficacy at different stages of upper motor neuron diseases, both in focal deficits and as adjuvant therapy in segmental and generalized spasticity. Therefore, the primary objective of this present study is to objectively quantify the improvement in walking ability and fatigue as an associated symptom in patients with spastic paraparesis caused by MS.

Methods

LINITOX was a multicenter, prospective, open-label low-intervention trial performed in patients with MS and spastic paraparesis of the lower limbs. The study was performed in daily clinical practice and was designed to evaluate the ability to walk and fatigue after infiltration of aboBoNT-A.

The clinical trial was authorized by the Spanish Agency for Medicines and Medicinal Products (Agencia Española de Medicamentos y Productos Sanitarios [AEMPS]) and approved by an ethics committee for clinical research with medicines. Moreover, in line with current legislation, the trial was publicly registered before initiation of recruitment (EudraCT number: 2018-003231-30).

The primary objective of the trial was to evaluate the effectiveness of infiltration of botulinum toxin for ability to walk in patients with MS and spasticity of the lower limbs. Effectiveness was evaluated at 4 weeks after the infiltration and during the following 12 months (or after 4 cycles) using the 6-Minute Walk Test (6MWT); a feasible, reproducible, and reliable measure in MS (Goldman et al, 2008), and a self-administered instrument for assessment of fatigue. The 12-Item Multiple Sclerosis Walking Scale (MSWS-12) was used since it is a reliable and valid patient-based measure of the impact of MS on walking (Hobart et al, 2003). Our secondary objective was to evaluate the effects on patients quality of life. Given the course of neurodegenerative disease, we did not evaluate long-term efficacy.

Other standard variables recorded included demographic data, degree of muscle spasticity, evaluated with Ashworth scale (MAS) (Harb et al, 2023), quality of life, evaluated with MSQoL-54 (Multiple

Sclerosis Quality of Life 54) scale (Vickrey et al,

1995), with of patients with spasticity at baseline and after completion of the study, and safety of botulinum toxin.

2.1 Study population

The study population comprised adult patients with MS-associated spastic paraparesis refractory to noninterventional measures and spasticity-related functional gait disorders.

2.2 Inclusion and exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria were as follows: agreement to participate in the study; age between 18 and 80 years; spastic paraparesis secondary to MS of any type; segmental spasticity ≥ 1 according to the Modified Ashworth Scale (MAS) in at least 1 muscle of the lower limbs; resistance to oral or non-pharmacological therapy; and an Expanded Disability Status Scale (EDSS) score between 2 and 7.5 (inclusive). In addition, participants had to have minimum or no cognitive impairment (score < 5 on the Pfeiffer Short Portable Mental State Questionnaire) to ensure that they could complete the questionnaires and undergo additional tests. The exclusion criteria were as follows: psychiatric disease that hampered participation in the trial; comorbidity that was life-threatening in the short term; osteoarticular disorder preventing physical activity; pregnancy or not using contraception during the study period; breastfeeding; absence of primary or secondary response; previously detected sensitivity to any type of botulinum toxin; other medical conditions that, in the investigator's opinion, could compromise the fulfillment of the study objectives and/or procedures involved in the protocol or prevent administration of botulinum toxin; and modifications to the treatment regimen of any drug that could interfere directly or indirectly with neuromuscular function during the 4 weeks before initiation of the study.

2.3 Intervention

The study intervention consisted of an ultrasound-guided infiltration of aboBoNT-A in patients with spastic paraparesis of the lower limbs according to the daily clinical practice of the department. Between 1 and 4 cycles per patient were undertaken, with an interval varying depending on the patient's needs and the investigator's opinion (always with at least 12 weeks between cycles).

Pharmacologic treatment of spasticity was permitted during the study, as were physical treatments for the main symptoms, that is, spasticity and fatigue, provided that the dose, or therapy regimen, was stable at the time of infiltration and unchanged until one month after administration.

Patients were evaluated over 12 months (4 treatment cycles in patients affected by the pandemic, see below for further information). The interval between cycles was at least 12 weeks and was based on clinical criteria. Each infiltration was reviewed 4–8 weeks after administration of each cycle. Between 1 and 4 cycles were administered depending on the reinfiltration interval.

The expected duration of participation was 12 months. The overall duration of the study was 42 months, from January 2019 to July 2022. The actual duration somewhat exceeded the expected duration owing to the delays caused by the COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting cancellation of appointments at health centers in March 2020 and subsequent months. Interruption of follow-up owing to the pandemic led to the suspension of care activity during these months. According to the indications of the AEMPS, every attempt was made to maintain the activity of the trial, guarantee health care for patients, ensure safety and well-being, and preserve the traceability of the actions implemented during the health emergency.

Given that the study patients were receiving immunosuppressants, the sponsor and the investigators felt that it would be wise to postpone visits, which were reprogrammed in the visit schedule of the clinical trial. Since the trial was performed under conditions of daily clinical practice, appointments were suspended owing to lockdown until patients' protection could be guaranteed at visits.

In the case of patients who did not complete the year of follow-up, this was extended, as were data collection and inclusion in the trial until 4 treatment cycles had been administered. This modification was recorded as an amendment to the protocol, in line with current administrative regulations (Fig. 1).

2.4 Botulinum toxin

The mean dose applied for treatment of spasticity of the lower limbs is 500 U of aboBoNT-A, which should be administered according to the investigator's experience. The ultrasound-guided intramuscular infiltration was delivered to those muscles affected by spasticity. The infiltration was repeated after 12 weeks depending on the patient's needs and the investigator's opinion, since the duration of the effect of botulinum toxin in spasticity of other causes is 12–16 weeks (Esquenazi et al, 2020; Ojardias et al, 2022; Turner-Stokes et al, 2020).

2.5 Outcome measures

Demographic data included age, disease type, and time since diagnosis. We also recorded the Expanded disability status scale (EDSS), sporting activity, disability status (Barthel index, recognized degree of disability and Dependency Law) membership of an MS association, active rehabilitation therapy, and therapy based on the main drugs associated with the main outcome measures, namely, fampiridine, baclofen, and/or nabiximols.

The outcome measures evaluate were the maximum distance a patient can walk in 6 minutes (6MWT), submaximal respiratory effort test through which the functional capacity of the individual in activities of daily living is evaluated; and changes in the score obtained in the MSWS-12 scale (self-administered scale that evaluates the patient's subjective capacity to walk, run and jump in the last two weeks). It consists of 12 items that are evaluated from 1 to 5 each and, when added together, give a minimum total of 12 (no impairment) and a maximum of over 60 (maximum impairment), which must then be transformed into a scale with a range of 0 to 100). Both variables were measured at 4-8 weeks after each infiltration, in relation to the baseline score and at 12 months after the onset of the process.

For the evaluation of spasticity per muscle assessed, the MAS scale (Modified Ashworth Scale) was used in each of the cycles.

At the beginning and end of the intervention, the quality of life score was obtained according to the MSQol-54 (Multiple Sclerosis Quality of Life 54) scale.

Finally, the occurrence of adverse reactions of any kind throughout the study was recorded.

2.6 Statistical analysis

The sample size necessary to obtain the desired statistical significance was calculated as follows. Since we were unable to find previous studies using the 6MWT as the primary outcome measure in patients with MS, we made suppositions to estimate the sample size considering studies on other diseases that use such test as the gold standard. Such studies consider clinically significant a 20% improvement in walking ability with respect to the baseline. Taking an alpha risk of 0.05 in a 2-tailed contrast to detect an approximately 20% improvement with a precision of ± 9 percent points, if we assume follow-up loss or of data for measurement of the primary objective not greater than 10%, the total number of patients to be included in the study was calculated to be 84.

In the exploratory analysis of the primary outcome measures, each patient is considered his/her own control, given that each distance covered is an individual characteristic of each cycle/patient. The analysis was always based on normally distributed data.

The hypothesis was analyzed based on the normality of the distribution for each combination of cycle and visit and using the Shapiro-Wilk test. To determine whether the treatment really did lead to an improvement, the hypotheses put forward were tested using the 2-tailed t test for paired samples based on the distance in the 6MWT, since it is assumed to be normal. To assess MSWS-12, we used the nonparametric Wilcoxon test, since we rejected a normal distribution for some groups. A Bonferroni correction was applied in both cases since we were performing several comparisons simultaneously. The significance level was as set for the other tests, ie, 95%.

In the case of the primary outcome measure, 6MWT, we found that between 9% and 9.5% of data were missing; the calculation was made using random forest predictive models, with a predictive power of 90.4% and 96.5.% in the validation. The outcome measure MSWS-12% cannot be modeled with sufficient precision. Missing data were not imputed.

2.7 Patient disposition

A total of 84 patients were included, 74 in Hospital Universitario de la Princesa and 10 in Hospital Universitario Puerta de Hierro. All eligible patients (i.e., who fulfilled the inclusion criteria) were included in the intention-to-treat analysis, irrespective of whether they adhered strictly to the protocol. A per protocol analysis was not undertaken because the trial was performed in daily clinical practice. Four patients were considered non-evaluable losses in the statistical analysis, that is, patients who signed the informed consent and who for different reasons (i.e., withdrawal of consent, incidental death, investigator's decision) did not receive the first dose of study medication (3 patients) and a patient who became pregnant during the study and was not included in the intention-to-treat analysis. A total of 214 treatment cycles were administered and analyzed (Fig. 2).

Results

The present study was started in January 2019. Interruption of follow-up owing to the COVID-19 pandemic led to the suspension of care activity during these months. According to the indications of the AEMPS, every attempt was made to maintain the activity of the trial, guarantee health care for patients, ensure safety and well-being, and preserve the traceability of the actions implemented during the health emergency.

In the case of patients who did not complete the year of follow-up, data collection and inclusion in the trial were extended for up to 4 treatment cycles. Missing data were extrapolated owing to this situation. Consequently, the analysis was performed by intention to treat and not per protocol.

3.1 Demographic characteristics

The demographic characteristics of the study population are shown in Table 1. The mean (standard deviation [SD]) age was 50 (10) years (Fig. 3); women accounted for 55% and men 45%. The most common disease type was relapsing-remitting (74%) (Fig. 4), with a mean time since diagnosis of 17 (9) years, 49% of patients engaged in sports, and 44% were actively working. Slightly more than half of the patients (53%) belonged to an MS association. The mean Barthel disability index was 91 (12), the mean percentage of recognized disability was 47%, and 20% were processing an application to be considered legally dependent. The mean score on the EDSS was 5 (2).

The mean (SD) number of muscles affected in the lower limbs was 3.13 (1.32), with a mean MAS of 1.56 (0.41). The upper limbs were also affected in 9% of cases. A mean of 2.53 (1.36) muscles per

session were infiltrated, the most frequent being the soleus and the medial gastrocnemius, with a mean dose of 429.9 U (177.74) of Dysport per session. The mean duration of the injections was 4.21 (1.48) months.

3.2 Exploratory analysis of the primary outcome measures

The results were evaluated between each of the cycles (period 1_1/1_2, 2_1/2_2/3_1/3_2,4_1/4_2) and between baseline and the end of follow-up (period 1_1/4_2). In both the 6MWT (absolute and percentage values) and the MSWS-12, we observed a statistically significant improvement in each treatment cycle (Table 2, Fig. 5), except in the second cycle in the MSWS-12 and third in the test 6MWT.

After receiving the treatment, the patients' condition improved by 11.34% in the 6MWT (by between 15 and 29 meters between visits, with statistically significant values recorded for cycles 1, 3, and 4), and fell 4.3 percentage points (between 4 and 6.6 percentage points, with statistically significant values recorded for cycles 1, 3, and 4) in the MSWS-12. Both improvements were statistically significant.

The exploratory analysis of the primary outcome measures (Fig. 6) showed that in both the 6MWT and the MSWS-12, the improvement was greater than 0 (mean), markedly indicating that treatment was efficacious. The comparison between cycles pointed to an improvement between the review after a month in the first infiltration,

and in the fourth (period 1_2 and period 4_2), that is, treatment not only did not lose efficacy after 4 applications, but it appears to be a cumulative benefit over cycles compare to baseline. According to the effects of the variables on the ability to walk (6MWT), the improvement was statistically significant in each cycle, except the third cycle. Similarly, the improvement was statistically significant between baseline and the end of follow-up.

As for the secondary outcome measures, we evaluated the intensity of spasticity according to the MAS. However, given the way the data were recorded, we could not test the hypotheses, perform a graphic analysis, or construct statistical models with the findings for degree of spasticity according to the MAS. Therefore, the analysis cannot be considered valid.

There was a significant difference between the baseline and final MSQoL-54 score. This increased by a mean of 3.91 (95% CI, 1.10, 6.73).

Once the exploratory analysis of the explanatory variables was performed, the only correlation considered strong was that between progressive-secondary disease and the 2 outcome measures, with the poorest results recorded for this disease type.

The walking capacity assessed by the 6MWT is negatively influenced by age and the association with baclofen intake but there is no evidence that gender or the intake of nabiximols or fampyridine does it. On the other hand, fatigue assessed by the MSWS test is positively influenced by sports practice or previous baclofen intake but there is no evidence that age or the intake of nabiximols or fampyridine can modify the test.

(Table 3, Fig. 7).

Discussion

Very few studies examine treatment of spasticity with botulinum toxin in MS, partly because the summary of product characteristics of the different pharmaceutical products does not include this indication (Fu et al, 2018), thus somewhat limiting use of the drug and associated research in care centers. However, in daily clinical practice, botulinum toxin is practically a standard treatment for focal spasticity in MS, and almost all authors approve the use of this agent in the lower limbs with a high

strength of recommendation (Fu et al, 2018; Comi et al, 2020; Dressler et al, 2017; Otero-Romero et al, 2016; Dashtipour et al, 2016). The main limitations affecting scientific evidence for the efficacy of botulinum toxin are heterogeneous study design and the impact of confounders, even though systematic reviews and meta-analyses confirm that botulinum toxin is an appropriate option for the treatment of spasticity affecting the lower limbs in MS. (Miguéns Vázquez, 2023)

The objective of the present study was to quantify the variations in walking capacity and intensity of fatigue related to walking capacity, after the administration of botulinum toxin in patients affected by spastic paraparesis in the lower limbs secondary to multiple sclerosis in any of its variants.

Our study shows an improvement in meters walked in the 6MWT (11.34% meters) test and a reduction in the fatigue score (6.86%) in each one of the treatment cycles, as well as between the beginning and the end of follow-up, irrespective of the latter's duration, which provides scientific evidence to regular clinical practice.

The onset of the effect of aboBoNT-A in spasticity occurs after 2-3 weeks and lasts for 3-4 months. The data from this trial, besides demonstrating the statistically significant improvement in walking capacity and fatigue, suggest that the effect of the aboBoNT-A does not disappear completely 4 months after the infiltration. The initial post-infiltration improvement does not disappear entirely over time, although the cycles last more than 3 months, whereby the patients begin with a slight advantage in the following infiltration, although no cumulative effect is observed with the different injections. This finding has not been specified in the literature, and reference is only made to the fact that a shorter interval between injections maximizes the effect of the treatment of spasticity with botulinum toxin (Trompetto et al, 2017; Novarella et al, 2022). Considering that aboBoNT-A has a temporary effect (Agencia Española de Medicamentos y Productos Sanitarios, 2022), it should be considered that the patients we are treating are in a healthcare circuit, with a high percentage of patients that work (44%) and who do sports (49%) and/or who belong to associations that provide physical therapies (53%). The improvement that we achieve in fatigue and walking capacity with the aboBoNT-A might be thought to facilitate the performance of other therapies or physical activity, and that even though are dealing with a degenerative disease and the toxin is a drug with a transient action, we achieve lasting functional improvements.

As occurs with general disability in patients with multiple sclerosis, the most important factor that modifies the walking capacity response to treatment with aboBoNT-A in the short term is the type of disease. In this trial we did not find significant differences between patients with primary-progressive and relapsing-remitting types of diseases, whereas patients with secondary-progressive type of disease obtained clearly poorer outcomes (a mean of 181 meters less walked) in the walk test and the MSWS 12 fatigue scale, which is concordant with the existing literature (Dashtipour 2016, Coincoloni 2014, Dressler 2017, Merziye 2020).

The poor prognosis factors in MS include male gender, age of presentation and being Afro-American, as well as the clinical symptoms resulting from infratentorial lesions (brain stem and cerebellum (Correa-Diaz et al, 2018). In our sample, gender does not condition the outcomes of the intervention, although age is also related to reduced walking capacity, of 3.8 meters less per year of age. This would need to be compared to the walking capacity of healthy individuals (Cerdeira, 2014), whose walking capacity diminishes by 15% as of the age of 60 years, although on account of the disease, our sample comprises mainly young patients, leading us to conclude that disease conditions this outcome.

Physical activity appears to be indirectly associated with better quality of life in people with MS and it is becoming one of the basic cornerstones of health education (Motl et al, 2009).. In this trial, patients who do sports walk a mean of 94 meters more, which could endorse this assertion. There seems to be a close relationship between physical activity, emotional status, pain, and fatigue. This trial shows that patients who do sports also score a mean of 10 points less on the MSWS 12 fatigue scale.

For the study's primary endpoint, walking capacity, the combination of treatment with baclofen or fampridine constitutes a poor-prognosis factor in the outcome of the intervention. This would be logical, since taking these drugs is associated with greater spasticity, leading us to assume that these patients present poorer functional statuses (Arriaza, 2023). There is evidence that the combination of therapeutic exercise and fampridine improves results in walking capacity, although there is currently no solid evidence and there is an unclarified interaction.

On the other hand, patients previously treated with nabiximols respond the same as those who have not previously taken any treatment for spasticity and fatigue, i.e., taking nabiximols does not modify outcomes, so considering that it is a drug indicated for moderate-severe spasticity and spasticity plus (Chan et al, 2022) syndrome, and that these patients improve just like the rest, Sativex could be a factor conditioning improvement if used in combination with botulinum toxin. Regarding changes in perceived fatigue in walking, we did not detect that any of these factors, i.e. age, fampridine, nabiximols or baclofen affect outcomes, although considering that the objective of treatment is above all to improve walking capacity, the study's design probably justifies this absence of clear evidence for or against.

With respect to overall functioning and quality of life, the prospective registry Aspire (Esquenazi et al, 2021) reported a statistically significant improvement on the Disability Assessment Scale (DAS) after administration of botulinum toxin in the lower limbs in the medium and long terms. This contrasts with the findings of Paoloni et al. (Paoloni et al, 2013), which reflect the absence of changes in the Barthel scale despite the improvement in spasticity. The systematic review of Ergul et al. (Ergul et al, 2020) specifically investigated whether the reduction in spasticity positively affected functioning in patients with MS, concluding that evidence on the beneficial effects of interventions to treat spasticity is very limited and of poor quality in terms of functional clinical outcomes in patients with MS. Our study reflects an improvement in the quality of life of patients according to the MSQoL-54 throughout the study. Considering that MS is a neurodegenerative disease, these results are encouraging.

Limitations

Among the limitations of the study is the absence of a control group in which a placebo could be used, which compromises the internal validity of the study. We cannot ensure that the changes we observed are the result of the intervention itself or are due to other interventions or factors that were not controlled for. However, the homogeneity of our sample and the constantly normal distribution minimize this limitation.

The interference of the COVID-19 pandemic on the performance of the trial led to an interruption of the protocol and withdrawal from follow-up in several cases, as well as generalized worsening of the clinical condition of patients with MS. The influence of these factors could not be quantified. Although the missing data were imputed using a highly reliable statistical model, the COVID-19 pandemic required the initial trial protocol to be modified and the analysis to be performed on an intention-to-treat basis and not per protocol. Consequently, the results may have been affected.

Conclusion

Our study provides statistical evidence that infiltration of aboBoNT-A to treat lower limb spasticity in MS patients is effective in the short term for both abilities to walk and reduction in fatigue. There are signs that the treatment could maintain a slight effect with repeated injections, although the limitations inherent to studies such as the present one prevents us from confirming this.

The improvement in walking ability is negatively affected by age and spasticity treatment with baclofen, as well as the expression of the variant of secondarily progressive disease. Outcomes improve after infiltration of botulinum toxin in the lower limbs for patients who do sport.

Fatigue decreases after treatment of lower limb spasticity with aboBoNT-A, especially in patients who do sport, and, possibly, in those who receive fampiridine. As with walking capacity, secondary-progressive disease, and concomitant treatment of spasticity with baclofen are associated with a poorer response to treatment.

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Table legends

Table 1. Baseline demographic characteristics.

Table 2. Variations in the 6MWT value in absolute and percent terms and in the MSWS-12 value for each of the treatment cycles.

Table 3. Effects of the variables cycle, gender, age, sports, disease type, and pharmacologic treatment on the primary variables.

Figure legends

Fig. 1. Timeline.

Fig. 2. Patient disposition.

Fig. 3. Distribution by age.

Fig. 4. Distribution by disease type.

Fig. 5. Results of hypothesis testing by comparing visits for the variable 6MWT (overall values) and the MSWS-12 test.

Fig. 6. Comparison of improvement between visits 1_2 and 4_2 and between cycles of the walking tests and fatigue. Treatment does not lose efficacy over time, but rather seems to be more efficacious.

Fig. 7. plm model of random effects in the 6MWT and the MSWS-12.